

Multimission Simulation Optimization:
Sensor Tracking Over Various Horizons

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Abstract

UAS technology is becoming very popular for military, government, search and rescue, and hobby purposes. Each of these fields might require tracking of a target in a given search space. Depending on what type of target is being tracked, the UAS sensor being used might vary. As is commonly known, sensors come with certain inaccuracies and susceptibility to noise. In tracking a target, the Kalman filter is known to be effective at predicting a target's future location based off of past movements. This research covers the task of flight path optimization using one sensor to track a moving target.

Nomenclature

P	error covariance matrix
θ	angle of movement of vehicle
u	external disturbances like accelerations
Q	covariance noise of the move process
R	covariance noise of the observation
t	change in time from the movement of the target
F	state transition model
H	observation model
w	noise in the move process
v	noise in the measurement
z	measurement of the true state
\tilde{y}	innovation or measurement residual
S	innovation (or residual) covariance
K	optimal Kalman gain

1. Introduction

This research, called “Sensor Tracking Over Various Horizons”, is one part of the larger group of students researching “Multimission Simulation Optimization”. It is performed in the Electrical Engineering Department of Brigham Young University.

The objective of this research is to find the optimal angle that a vehicle should take per time step to efficiently track a moving target through a series of steps. The target will be considered

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efficiently tracked when the error covariance of the target's state estimate is minimized at every time step, and the error covariance sequentially decreases over all the time steps taken. The steps will be planned out in horizons, which project forward the future movements of a target as both the target and vehicle travel.

For this document's purposes, the sensor to be used will be a simple relative range sensor from vehicle to target. Through testing on the resulting error covariance matrix, it was found that this type of sensor works sufficiently with only one look ahead step (see "Kalman Filter" section below). The new location of the vehicle through each horizon will be optimized using the optimizer *fmincon*. After having optimized the preset amount of horizons, the optimizer will start a second optimization with the vehicle having moved to the end of the first set of horizons. The next starting angle will be warm started to conserve on function counts. Additionally, the next iteration will start with the error covariance matrix from the previous iteration.

A. Prior Work

Previous research has been performed on tracking vehicle movements with respect to a global position using Kalman filtering. This filter helps to improve the localized position of a vehicle by assessing the errors in the state space values.¹ This technique is used in Google's self driving car to detect the presence of other vehicles in its near vicinity. Additionally, Google's self driving car uses Kalman filters to predict the future movements of other cars at a close proximity.

In the field of localization and mapping of unmanned aerial systems, trajectory planning has not been as heavily researched.² Those that have researched trajectory planning define the goal as minimizing "the estimation error spanning a finite time horizon".² This is similar to how I define my objective in this paper, that the error covariance will be reduced through each time step over a set of horizons. Another research paper, by Tian, also deals with the idea of look ahead steps, but in an application of organizing various missions.³ The missions are set out in a layered fashion with the highest priority mission as the first objective and so forth. In my project's scope, I will only deal with one type of mission objective.

2. Methodology

A. Optimization Approach

The optimization problem presented in this report can be formulated as shown below:

Minimize: The error covariance of the distance sensor from one dynamic vehicle to one target with linear movements.

W.R.T.: The angle of movement of the vehicle

Constraints: Lower bound of 0° . Upper bound of 360°

The approach taken involves a main project file, a function file to be optimized, and a separate function for the Kalman state filter which will be described below. The function file takes in the design variables, puts them into usable variables for the function, and defines the next movement

of the vehicle. Additionally passed in from the main project file are scalar variables for controlling the step size of both the vehicle and target, the number of total steps to be taken in the simulation, the number of look ahead steps to be used in each optimization cycle before movement, the number of targets, and the number of vehicles.

B. Design Variables

The singular design variable for this optimization algorithm is the next movement angle (θ) of the vehicle. By predicting ahead according to the pre-specified amount of look-ahead steps that the target will take, the next angular movement of the vehicle will be optimized to allow minimization of the summed values in the error covariance matrix (P) (see Figure 1 below for an illustration of look-ahead steps).

Figure 1. Different look-ahead steps

When the design variable value is input to the objective function through *fmincon*, the relative distance between the target and the vehicle is calculated. After this calculation, the Kalman filter function provides the updated states of the target along with the associated error covariance matrix of that target.

How *fmincon* selected points is shown below in Figure 2. Since *fmincon* only has the ability to influence the angle of motion, each tested vehicle step (black x's) is always at the pre-defined radius away from the prior vehicle's location (cyan circles). *Fmincon* tests around this cyan circle until the gradient of the error covariance drops below the value for convergence. For cleanliness, the cyan circles will not be shown in future plots.

Figure 2. Example of angle selection

C. Objective Function

Generally, the objective function initially takes in the design variable guess of vehicle angular movement, and outputs the sum of all the values from the error covariance matrix. In order to reach that final output sum, it needs to run the Kalman filter function to get out a potential error covariance. The steps of the Kalman filter are listed below.

1. Kalman Filter

a. Setup

In setting up the Kalman filter equations, there are several parameters that need to be defined beforehand. These are shown in the nomenclature section at the beginning of this document. Specifically, they are the state space values of the target, external disturbances, the covariance noise of the move process, the covariance noise of the observation, the state transition model, the observation model, the move process noise, and the measurement noise. The state space values were set up as target x position, target y position, target x velocity, and target y velocity.

$$x = [x, y, \dot{x}, \dot{y}]^T$$

The target position values changed with each iteration of *fmincon*, while the velocities stay constant at 1 unit/time step. With this simulation, I ignored any effect of external disturbances (*u*) for this research. The observation model (*H*) was a matrix of the Jacobian of my measurement values:

$$H = \left[\frac{dr}{dx_t}, \frac{dr}{d\dot{x}_t}, \frac{dr}{dy_t}, \frac{dr}{d\dot{y}_t} \right]$$

$$\frac{dr}{dx_t} = \frac{x_t - x_v}{(x_t^2 - 2x_t x_v + x_v^2 + y_t^2 - 2y_t y_v + y_v^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\dot{x}_t} = 0$$

$$\frac{dr}{dy_t} = \frac{y_t - y_v}{(x_t^2 - 2x_t x_v + x_v^2 + y_t^2 - 2y_t y_v + y_v^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

$$\frac{dr}{d\dot{y}_t} = 0$$

Where *r* is the range value from vehicle to target, and *x_t* and *x_v* represent the target position and vehicle position respectively. The error covariance is initialized with equal values along the diagonal. This gives enough uncertainty for the optimizer to minimize.

b. Predict

In the predict stage, there are two main equations that need to be defined. They are the predicted state estimate and the predicted estimate covariance

$$x_{pred} = Fx_{pred} + u$$

$$P_{pred} = FP_{init}F^T + Q$$

where x_{pred} is the predicted state space vector and P_{init} is the initial error covariance matrix.

c. Measure

In the measure stage, there are two main equations that are used they are the measurement residual and the residual covariance

$$y = z - Hx_{pred}$$

$$S = HP_{pred}H^T + R$$

where z represents the actual input measurement from the sensor. The measurement residual gives the difference between the actual measurements and the predicted state values multiplied by the observation matrix.

d. Update

The update stage has three equations that are used. They are the optimal Kalman gain, the updated state estimate, and the updated estimate covariance.

$$K = P_{pred}HS$$

$$x_{upd} = x_{pred} + Ky$$

$$P_{upd} = (I - KH)P_{pred}$$

where I represents an identity matrix at the same size as the error covariance matrix. This last equation is the conversion from the prior error covariance to the posterior error covariance. This updated error covariance is what is summed in the optimizer as the potential optimized value.

D. Constraints

The constraints of this objective function are simple bound constraints with 0° as the lower bound and 360° as the upper bound. These bounds prevent *fmincon* from finding angles that are at excessively high and repetitive values. There is no need for equality or inequality constraints for this optimization process.

E. Convergence

The convergence criteria of each horizon step is that the value of the gradient of the objective function will be smaller than $1e-6$. With the current setup for the objective function, there are two places that the optimizer could possibly converge to as the minimum. This is illustrated below in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Example graph of potential local minima.

It can be seen in the red ovals of the above figure that there are two apparent local minima, where one is logically the correct minimum, and the other is the result of an imprecise selection of bounds for that iteration. If the optimizer tests an angle that is past the climax of that area, it can potentially get stuck there, thinking that an angle of zero degrees is the absolute minimum for every iteration thereafter due to the warm starting technique I use for each successive iteration (see introduction). To avoid this problem, initial angles are consciously chosen that will avoid the area with the incorrect local minimum.

3. Results

I test my optimizer and function with three different path directions of the target. They are all linear movements with adjustments of 45 degrees in between each. These paths, along with the steps that the vehicle took as a result of the target's motions are shown below in Figures 4, 5 and 6.

Figure 4. Target movement direction of 0 degrees.

Figure 5. Target movement direction of 90 degrees.

Figure 6. Target movement direction of 45 degrees.

From these previous three graphs, it is noticeable that this distance sensing vehicle prefers to travel in a near orthogonal direction to the path of motion of the target. Additionally, notice how at the beginning of the path movements, the dispersion of angles tested is greater than in all later iterations (black x's on above figures). Due to the warm starting technique, the later iterations only required around two function calls to converge to the minimum. The optimum angle from the previous run of *fmincon* is fed into the next iteration as the initial guess, thus limiting the dispersion and number of *fmincon* tests needed to find an adequate movement angle.

In the bar graph below (Figure 7), it is shown that the total uncertainty after each step decreased steadily through all iterations. The methodology that causes this is similar to the warm starting of the initial guess; the final minimized error covariance matrix from the previous iteration is fed into the next iteration as its own starting value. This bar graph shows that the optimal vehicle direction that *fmincon* finds at each iteration is in fact causing a decrease in the overall error covariance.

Figure 7. The decrease in the summed error covariance matrix through each iteration.

The relevance of this result shown above is that the optimizer was finding a good enough solution because it was satisfying the mission objective defined in the introduction section. Specifically, “The target will be considered efficiently tracked when the error covariance of the target state estimate is minimized at every time step, and the error covariance sequentially decreases over all the time steps taken”. This virtual distance sensor would function normally at any distance from the target, but due to the imperfect nature of real-life distance sensors, moving so far away from the target would induce inaccuracies in the measurement values. However, these results satisfy the scope of what this report set out to accomplish.

4. Conclusion/Next Steps

The optimizer used in this report provides an accurate output of the minimum error covariance for all iterations. It performed the same for each target angle of movement. The next goal of this optimizer is to optimize the vehicle path with multiple targets moving in nonlinear motions. This adds a certain amount of complexity to efficiently tracking the targets, so it will become necessary to consider increasing the number of tracking vehicles to the field. More vehicles will be added if the decrease in error covariance on the target states is not large enough through successive iterations. Additionally, the type of sensor that each vehicle carries will vary, so different tracking strengths can be considered.

5. References

- ¹Al-Khedher A., Mohammad. "Hybrid GPS-GSM Localization of Automobile Tracking System."
International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol. 3.No. 6
(2011)Print.
- ²Huang, Shoudong, et al. "Multi-Step Look-Ahead Trajectory Planning in SLAM: Possibility and
Necessity." (2005): Pg. 1091. Print.
- ³Tian, X., Y. Bar-Shalom, and K. R. and Pattipati. "Multi-Step Look-Ahead Policy for Autonomous
Cooperative Surveillance by UAVs in Hostile Environments." Vol. 5.No. 1 (2010): Pg. 3. Print.